

Customers' satisfaction level regarding e-commerce in Bangladesh during COVID-19

Tanzila Rahman Lubna

Abstract

COVID-19 is not a matter of fear and damage only; it also affects the economy of the country. But the fact, it also tends to bring some change in the economy besides the challenges. Due to the lockdown during COVID-19, the online business which is called e-commerce in a broader sense becomes accelerated. There are many entrepreneurs who start-up online businesses and people also get involved in selling too. So, to keep improvement and sustainability, the service provider must ensure customer satisfaction. To measure the customer satisfaction level, I preferred to study with the SERVQUAL model with the perception of respondents. The questionnaire is divided into two categories; one is the personal profile of the respondents and their perception regarding tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Except for the tangibility factor customers are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with the attributes. So, only customer satisfaction of tangibility factor is not enough to build long-term customer relationships and stable business growth. It is high time for the online professional and service provider to ensure broad study on customer and probe the desire, it is not enough to figure out the desire only, and they must ensure filling it to make the customer satisfied regarding the product and service of e-commerce in Bangladesh during COVID-19.

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Introduction

Ecommerce is an online platform of business where you can buy or sell goods through a particular website or social media tools (E-commerce guide). The online business got accelerated during COVID-19 whether other businesses got into trouble, or the global business became volatile. Many small entrepreneurs or individual have started their businesses on virtual platforms appearing as e-commerce companies now. As a result, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the growth of e-commerce transactions is increasing 10 times than the normal situation. The COVID-19 problem transformed the nature of corporate activity and stimulated global internet commerce. According to researchers, there is about 52% of consumers have tried to avoid gathering places like physical shopping. Additionally, some people approx. 36% are avoiding outdoor transactions until they take the vaccine of COVID 19. Customer perception of the different products has been changed due to the effect of Corona virus, which means the necessity of some products is get very high while other products became less necessitated Bhatti, et, al, (2020). According to Vrender (2016), as the internet changes, so do consumers' preferences and online usage influences what they buy. Gaffar (2016) mentioned that the ICT sector plays a significant role in the development of finance and business, thus contributing to the future growth of developing economies like Bangladesh. According to Rashid MH (2020) the fourth industrial revolution and the digital economy are emerging in Bangladesh. This is a pick time to establish an online business in the country and has a greater acceptance by all. After all the customers have some sort of complain and recommendation as they might not satisfied with the support and service. As a part of this e-commerce platform, I figure out some findings which might have a great influence on the service provider if the research finds the root cause and the level of customer satisfaction. If the customers are not satisfied, it will ultimately affect the business sales and growth that do not bring blessing to the economy. The major objectives of this research are to unfold the customers' perception regarding the support service of e-commerce in Bangladesh and advise some sort of recommendation based on the findings. There will be a great support for the online business host/booth to manifold their marketing, selling, and business policies.

Literature Review

Human behavior changes as a result of COVID-19. The business platform is modified by COVID-2019. Man is, in general, resistant to change. People are being forced to alter their lifestyles as a result of COVID-19, including their dietary habits, dress choices (such as masks), social withdrawal, and public speech. People began to rely heavily on the virtual world as walking outside became hazardous to their health. When you're at home, you can conduct many kinds of business online, including shopping, leisure, education, and other activities to complete the necessary shopping E-commerce serves as a link between consumers and physical stores. Numerous e-commerce service providers act as a conduit for online shopping. The BTRC study indicates that during the COVID-19 period, there was an increase in the number of internet subscriptions. However, a relatively small percentage of subscribers use the internet to make purchases online. The remaining subscribers utilize the internet for other purposes, including jobs and education (Ahsan and Arafat, 2021). The Bangladeshi e-commerce market's potential size and a positive indication of ecosystem development have led to some outstanding valuations for the nation's developing e-commerce. Whether these valuations are generally cautious or are a product of an overly optimistic "bubble" is a topic of significant discussion. Bangladesh is a developing nation, yet some sectors of the business community have adopted technology with some degree of success (Mohiuddin, 2014). Consumers can share their opinions and experiences online thanks to the widely used online user feedback platforms, which automate and enhance the digital WOM process (Duan et al. 2009). Contrary to online user reviews, increased product variety is frequently identified as a key long-tail supply side

factor in the research (Anderson 2006). Due to the Internet, it is now more practical and efficient to provide consumers with a considerably wider range of products through online channels than through physical storefronts (Brynjolfsson et al. 2006). Given the potential interaction impact between product variety and online user evaluations, Brynjolfsson et al. (2011) recommend taking demand-side factors into account in addition to product diversity when examining changes in consumption patterns. Due to the low cost of active consumer search via Internet channels, their analysis emphasizes the need for stabilizing product diversity when analyzing the long-tail effects of demand-side factors. User preferences might therefore be influenced by online user evaluations, one of the key demand-side factors, depending on the number of products available. Some recent long-tail studies did not express the potential consequences of changing product variety since they adjusted for it during the study period (Ghose and Gu 2007, Brynjolfsson et al. 2011, Tucker, and Zhang 2007). According to prior studies, the impact of online user reviews may be influenced by their intricate interactions with a variety of products, even if this has not been fully studied in the current research. Additionally, current research reveals that online user reviews affect products differently depending on their level of popularity (Duan et al. 2009, Zhao et al. 2008, Zhu and Zhang 2010). Customers always expect service providers to be reliable, quick, reassuring, and caring, and the SERVQUAL model helps service providers understand how customers feel (Rouf et al., 2019).

Methodology of the Study

The study is structured as empirical research, which includes both quantitative and qualitative components. I designed the questionnaires to gather data for this purpose using 22 sets of questions or statements based on the SERVQUAL Model (Rouf et al., 2019). The five characteristics of service quality that the model is based on are tangibility, dependability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Bitner and Hubbert, 1994). The respondents are questioned on a Likert scale about a five-point scale. The respondents are asked to rate on a scale from highly dissatisfied (score 1) to very satisfied (score 5) in order to gauge the level of perception (score 5). SPSS was used to examine the data (16.0 version). I obtained the data I was looking for by giving the respondent a paper with a questionnaire. Any empirical research project must adhere to a clear and detailed methodology, which is a set of guidelines for sample size, sample selection, and data collection. The approach used for the current investigation is provided in the sections below in chronological order.

Study Area

I chose the Bogura district as the study's sample area since it is convenient. To gather the information, I visited markets, shops, and educational institutions.

Population and Sample

The participants in the current study are those who utilize e-commerce or shop online. 100 respondents who have expertise with internet shopping provided the information.

Data Collection

Source of information: Both primary and secondary sources of data were used to perform the study. Through the use of a structured questionnaire created using the SERVQUAL paradigm, primary data were gathered. This study includes a variety of secondary data types. The websites listed below, as well as numerous periodicals, are sources of secondary information. For the investigation, we employed a convenient sampling strategy. I have chosen non-probability sampling techniques to gather the right data.

Analysis and Result Discussion

The analysis has done and categories into two parts. One is the evaluation of personal profile and their shopping activities and another on is their feedback regarding the service of ecommerce. All the analysis and interpretation lead the outcome of the study.

Figure 01: Personal profile of the respondents

The above figure 01 shows the demographic description of the respondents. There is 67 male and 33 female participate in the survey. From them most of them are student and the number is 57; 30 respondents are from service only 6, 7 respondents belong to business and housewife respectively. It was a major fact that how much they expand for online shopping and the majority goes for below BDT 3,000; the number is 71. 19 respondents spend BDT 3,000 – BDT 10,000, 8 respondents spend BDT 10,000 – BDT 20,000 and only 2 respondents found who spend more than BDT 20,000 per month in online shopping. Number of 76 respondents having 1-3 transaction per month, there are 15 respondents having 4-5 transaction in a month, there only 5 and 4 respondents having 6-7 and more than 8 transactions in a month respectively. From the total number of respondents only 8 respondents pass SSC, 31 respondents from HSC, 43 respondents are from graduation and 18 from post-graduation level that means all the respondents are educated while they are from different education level.

Table 01: Customer’s perception of tangibility

Variables	Attributes	Perception (Mean Score)	Mean Score
Tangibility	Product & service (types) provided by seller (available online)	3.92	3.74
	Advertisement	4.00	
	Virtual point of selling (PoS)	3.44	
	Websites’ acts (design and visibility)	3.60	

The table 01 shows the perception of tangibility statements. Respondents marked 3.92 means they are satisfied with the availability of production and service in online. The means value of Advertisement and Websites’ acts is 4.00 and 3.60 respectively which imply respondents are also satisfied with these attributes. Respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied about the Virtual point of selling (PoS) and the mean score is 3.44. The overall mean score of tangibility

is 3.74 that mean the users are satisfied with the tangibility of e-commerce in BD during COVID-19.

Table 02: Customer's perception of reliability

Variables	Attributes	Perception (Mean Score)	Mean Score
Reliability	Keeping their promises	3.18	3.17
	Error free product/service	3.07	
	Sincerity regarding the delivery	3.34	
	Motion of work	3.28	
	Free from Fraud	2.99	

The table 02 shows the perception of reliability statements. Respondents marked 3.18 regarding the promise of seller and which implies neutral feedback. The users put neutral feedback for error free product or service, sincerity regarding the delivery, motion of work and the mean score are 3.07, 3.34, and 3.28 respectively. The means score 2.99 of free from fraud implies that they are not only neutral but also dissatisfied too. The overall mean score of reliability is 3.17 that mean the users are neither dissatisfied nor satisfied with the reliability of e-commerce in BD during COVID-19.

Table 03: Customer's perception of responsiveness

Variables	Attributes	Perception (Mean Score)	Mean Score
Responsiveness	Eagerness to Help Customer	3.39	3.31
	Answer to Customer Query	3.31	
	Availability of personnel (Instant support service)	3.19	
	Cooperation of Service Provider	3.34	

The table 03 shows the perception of responsiveness. Respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied regarding the eagerness to help customer, answer to customer query, availability of personnel (Instant support service) and cooperation of service provider and their mean score are 3.39, 3.31, 3.19 and 3.34 respectively. The overall mean score of responsiveness is 3.31 that mean the users are neither dissatisfied nor satisfied with the responsiveness of e-commerce in BD during COVID-19.

Table 04: Customer's perception of assurance

Variables	Attributes	Perception (Mean Score)	Mean Score
Assurance	Friendly Behavior	3.87	3.42
	Safety Transaction	3.49	
	Knowledge of Personnel	3.07	
	Consistent Performance	3.27	

The table 04 shows the perception of responsiveness. The means score of friendly behavior is 3.87 which means users are satisfied with the behavior of sellers and relevant bodies. Users also partially satisfied as the mean score is 3.49. Users have the neutral feedback against

knowledge of personnel and performance consistency and the mean value are 3.07 and 3.27 respectively. The overall mean score of assurance is 3.42 which conceded to partially satisfy with the assurance of e-commerce in BD during COVID-19. But this does not confirm the satisfaction as the mean value is below 3.5.

Table 05: Customer’s perception of empathy

Variables	Attributes	Perception (Mean Score)	Mean Score
Empathy	Individual Attention to Customer by Seller	3.16	3.34
	Operation Hours	3.07	
	Personal Attention by contact Window	3.41	
	Seller’s Feeling to Customer Needs and Wants	3.39	
	Their Interest to Sale/Serve	3.67	

The table 05 shows the perception of empathy. Users are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied regarding the individual attention to customer by seller and operation hour as their mean score are 3.16 and 3.07. Users are partially satisfied with the personal attention of contact window where mean score is 3.41. The mean score of seller’s feeling to customer needs and wants 3.39 which considered as partially satisfied. But seller’s interest makes the users satisfied and means score is 3.67. The overall mean score of assurance is 3.34 that mean the users are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with the empathy of e-commerce in BD during COVID-19.

Figure 02: Customer’s satisfaction level regarding the e-commerce in BD during COVID-

19

The above figure 02 shows that 13% respondents are satisfied with the service of e-commerce and 52% are satisfied and 29% of people marked neutral. So, it is very clear that the overall satisfaction level of users is good. There only 5% and 1% of users who are dissatisfied and very dissatisfied respectively. It meant only 6% of users are dissatisfied with the service of e-commerce in BD during COVID-19.

Recommendation and Conclusion

The findings of the research clearly showed that users are really satisfied with the product and service of e-commerce. But the result showed us different picture when we probe the respondents with 22 individual statements and the maximum feedback became average which means they are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Respondents are satisfied with the tangible features of e-commerce service where mean score is 3.74. Respondents are really neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with the reliability (mean score 3.17), responsiveness (mean score 3.31), assurance (mean score 3.42) and empathy (mean score 3.34). The overall satisfaction level is good but this not good enough if the industry wants to move long way. The authority and relevant concern must emphasize on individual statements or points. Their lifestyle is changing day to day and the standard of living going up. So, the seller should analyze the customer wants and take fruitful actions. So must take care of the reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy and only tangibility is not enough to build long-term relationship with the customers. E-commerce is one of Bangladesh's fastest-growing sectors. However, only online shopping has seen a bigger increase in popularity during COVID-19, while other industries are stable. Therefore, a variety of elements, such as fare price, product quality, and durability, trust, and security, etc., affect buyers' behavior when they shop online. That was a great wave that people turn into online shopping during COVID-19, so we should nurse this opportunity as we grabbed it. This research will be a great guideline for them to where, how, and what should need to improve. The future study may conduct on large volume of respondents covering the several part of the country.

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